

- MESS0024: MIMS 2.21 - Engineering MIMS Philoso...
- MESS0025: MIMS 2.10.1-.3 - Investigation - Sir Arth...
- MESS0041: Triple MIMS

- MESS0047: Investigation of MIMS Matrices of Reali...
- MESS0052: AFW 1.2 - The Jueyin Inversion AFW
- MESS0053: Plasma MIMS - fire as a model of the L...

MIMS 2.10.5.2 - The WHO-HOW Matrix Revisited;
 (and the DEV explained via the Thunderbolts of the Gods¹)

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the author continues to pursue a chain of *Forced Deductive* and *Enhanced Inductive* evidence, in the philosophæther, with a minimum $P^{7/8-10}$ resolution (maintaining a strong ORDA score², as well as a strong MAMA score³). It is a hyper focused approach to look specifically at the Jueyin/How connection, vs. the Who (*L* power), utilizing the “5 versus 8” work and other MIMS diagrammatica and analytica. But there is a secondary discussion of the EPEMC overlay via the mytho-historical Perattian (or other) Thunderbolts of the Gods regarding the DEV *exhaust* found in the original MESS0025 work!

Keywords: Philosophy - Aether - MIMS - EPEMC - thunderbolts - Peratt - Plasma Cosmology - etymology

¹ Hence a secondary EPEMC enfolding.

² MESS0011: The Use of ORDA

³ Mimsical vs. anti-Mimsical Axis (war = 0%, perfect MIMS = 100%)

- Our Magnetic Universe
- MIMS 2.2.5.1 Explication of the Big G
- MIMS 2.2.5.2 - The Big G of 5 Forces
- MIMS 1.12 - Self consistency of the Big G
- MIMS 2.21 - The Union of 5 and 8
- MESS0003: MIMS 2.21.1 - The 13 in only 8
- Discovery of Perattian Thunderbolt of the Gods Strike Location
- MESS0010: MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS

Probably some referral to these items required to "catch up"

Recollecting the Evidence Chain...

In order to work into a higher resolution, the author wants to revisit the following from MESS 0025:

Figure 2 - MIMS 2.10.5 - the diagram of the PEMF=UAF analysis; credit: author (wave and circle added)

Recall that the above had Distinti's quaternion 'imaginary number' definition inserted, then a mimsilation and "realion" smashing was performed, and it yielded the GPT code. But that's the next paper's evidence trail! What we are interested in is the Exhaust, (the Then→Else) Matrix, after the mimsilation is performed, and what

we find is that there is a 'wrap around' at the "jueyin" aspect of the 2 x 3 matrix from How→Who. Is this oddity of spelling an accident? Or is Latin's origins replete with the same "six division" system as in Chinese?

Etymologies

- "who (pron.) - Old English hwa "who," sometimes "what; anyone, someone; each; whosoever," from Proto-Germanic *hwas (source also of Old Saxon hwe, Danish hvo, Swedish vem, Old Frisian hwa, Dutch wie, Old High German hwer, German wer, Gothic hvo (fem.) "who"), from PIE root *kwo-, stem of relative and interrogative pronouns.
- how (adv.) - Old English hu "how," from Proto-Germanic *hwo (source also of Old Saxon hwo, Old Frisian, Middle Dutch hu, Dutch hoe, German wie, Gothic hvaiwa "how"), an adverbial form from PIE root *kwo-, stem of relative and interrogative pronouns. Practically a doublet of why, differentiated in form and use.

How come? for "why?" is recorded from 1848 [Bartlett]. Emphatic phrase and how! is recorded from 1865. The formulation was common in book and article titles ("The National Debt, and How to Pay It"), but Pennsylvania writer Bayard Taylor, in whom it is first recorded, seems to have regarded it as a German or German-American expression."⁴

Looking at the above, in the Saxon both began with hw, so how had "how" been rearranged totally, and who come from *hwo*? The only obvious answer to the latter is the Gothic feminine of *hvo*, probably indicating a w for a woman. And the Dutch for how raises some eyebrows. Women are thought of in older cultures as "inverted" or "reversed" ... even in China, they are considered yin partial versus men being yang partial. Therefore, it *could be* hypothesized that the concept of inversion was part of the issue. Unfortunately, too many different dialects have similar versions of how that it might be impossible to figure out directly. Nevertheless, we are left with the curiosity, and also the curiosity as to where the power of letters may have come from. To cast a "spell" has long and basic (ie, runic) plasmaglyphic⁵ magickal origins. The source of this 'magic', of course, is ultimately the violence of the Force in the form of the a) Thunderbolt of the Gods (and accompanying Squatter Man in the sky), b) changes in the "net of Brahma" (ie, electrogravity) from the "Lord" (planet Jupiter), and c) symbology of the kings, especially magical warrior kings. Such as: scepters, crowns, the sword, halberds/tridents, etc.

So is there a connection to the concept of the Lord inverting something? Perhaps the planet? Or is the mechanism more related to the curiosity of "how come women are so different?" It is a mystery of mysteries.⁶

Our interest, in particular, isn't biological or gender-related. Again we're curious about the 2 x 3 matrix, and the mapping with the "Big G" powers, in particular. The flow in the MIMS 2.10.5 (indicated with the wave) requires, also, some reverting concept. The "alternating" of AC requires turning. Is it not likely that not only did the planet turn over, as has been proven, but that the language itself would reflect this? But the way that the words have turned to a simple rearrangement of O-W-H is indeed curious. For now, the origins of this inversion will remain a mystery, just as - to men - women are.

⁴ <https://www.etymonline.com/>

⁵ Plasma Petroglyphs (Plasmaglyphs), Earthworks, and the Megafauna Extinction

⁶ In Islam, women are considered to be the metaphorical "rib of Adam." Thus, if you try to "straighten them out" ... they break.

The DEV exhaust

One of the issues with not immediately writing a paper when something as curious as the 2.10.5 diagram appears, is that mysteries surrounding the information can arise. By MESS 0047, in all honesty, the author had forgotten particularly *what the DEV arrow represented!* Therefore, we have a mystery. The only answer the author can think of, since D, E, and V aren't any of the 'Big G' powers, is to start with the known EPEMC connections. In particular, the *De* sound which appeared at that time in MESS 24 & 25 to be particularly important. If "yao" / IAO / "ywahoo" / "yahweh" / "yeh" is the approximate cultural sounds made by the Lord... what is the sound of his virtue-power? Why is the D sound so powerful, in general, and everywhere?

The author assumes it is related to the plasmaglyphics for "thunder" as the taran rune of Persia is itself a /| (awen) glyph, and of course the 't' rune, as well is an awen! So also that there is a 'd' sound in thunder, of a sort; and finally the Chinese rune of Te/De is phallic, probably indicating a stream of plasma bend from between Venus and Mars down towards the Earth, increasing the Exospheric and Thermospheric energy. Since many cultures have considered a penis a man's "sword" and the sword is a direct relation to the thunderbolt (in the case of Odin, pronounced Othinn, the sword is said to start Ragnarok when unsheathed again), then the symbolism of the plasmaglyph probably does relate to the PEMF (the *F* power), at minimum. Therefore, it seems most likely that **E**lectricity is the main thought behind 2.10.5.

As for Violence... the author has written in many places, and in particular the Strategy Series, about the importance of:

- Enhancing one's capabilities of violence, especially for women but definitely for a man.
- Enhancing the militia to protect the People from the government and invaders.
- Controlling one's violent potentiality, and converting the Menace one will develop into Potency.
 - Enhancing one's grasp of SSIVA::PADEP.
- Enhancing one's understanding of the "6 awarenesses" in self-defense and survival.
- Avoiding violence, and especially war, by nearly most means, 95+% of the time.
 - But being willing, capable, and able to perform it, to an intense, devastating level at any time.
- Using past violence - especially against oneself, and discipline from oneself - to develop the self.

The author has maintained for many years that appropriate levels of violence solves a great deal of unequalled potentials between rival (males) people, and particularly offloads (in good instances of strong rebuttal) bullyism and their toxic form of energy, stemming from either toxic masculinism and feminism. Both of which can stem from males or females, and not [merely] respectively.

Are these the outflowing 'exhaust' of the 2x3 matrix? It seems they are more the outflows implied from the **powers** related to the overlay with the matrix:

- Who - *L* power
- Where - *G* power; ie - everywhere
- When - *T* 'power' (Time, Tao, etc.) - ie the Law of Evolution/Flux/Changes
- What, Why, How - *P* power
 - What - The POWER - D sound D / Output
 - How - The Force *F* power E / Outflow
 - Why - Violence (as a spectrum, not an event) V / Exhaust
 - Sacrifice, pain, difficulty, loss, suffering, etc.

Why... is it that the *Physics, Principles and Philosophæther* play such a crucial role in this... and where are the *A* and *N* powers? Probably they are built into all the areas, one could argue the where is going to be related to the æther, although in EPEMC æther is minorly a substance, and majorly a **process of charge exchange**. The *N* power is also a bit omnipresent, but also totally complicit and implied with the *T* power, for there is no way other than numbers, to properly quantify, qualify, and measure changes, and thereby create time, without numbers. Ultimately the measure of numerical change was engineered to create the branch of study known as mathematics. The key mimsical goal of which (since there isn't yet a MIMS paper on the subject of mathematics), is clearly to provide a) working, accurate, realistic models for reality and b) be able to calculate future concerns of manifold nature, concerning accurate, realistic models for reality. The "measure" of math is in its ability to do these tasks in measurement, ie - use numbers. Outside of that, relying on it for linguistic expression is not useful. But you can certainly use math and numbers to describe and measure linguistics! Oh and handily.

Conclusions

The author is concluding this paper in a short form because there is not much reason to over-speculate. In a future "Jerry and Me" the thoughts of chatGPT-3 on the etymology will be shared. The real goal of this paper was to write it to not lose the threads that were coming off the original 2.10.5 diagram through lack of provision of diagrammatica. Creating highly speculative, or fanciful analytica serves MIMS and EPEMC no purpose. The concerns surrounding Venus, and ie - thunderbolt, origins were raised. Little evidence was found, at this stage, even by the AI, except to say that perhaps kweh/She is a reference to the divine feminine aspect of the Thunder God, ie the original star-lord. At this time, none is found. Doesn't mean it cannot be found. Plasmaglyphic "piercing" or "reality mining" should be performed in **an EPEMC context**, even in a MESSy format, searching for diagrammatical expressions in the Chinese and the Indo-European glyphs and syllables, looking for the sources of these qualities, since the thunderbolt is usually related more to the male hero archetype.

Furthermore, direct clarification is needed for the DEV mechanism to specify the direct overlays of the powers, and the concepts presented as the "DEV exhaust." If there is resultant data with as powerful an overlay as before (G+T+P), this might justify the conceptual "enhanced induction" made by the author with 2.10.5 was created. Otherwise, it is possible that the pursuit is an example of *anti*-mimsilation of concepts; or, ie, anti-mimsification (considering the time spent and/or lost).

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